

Lack of Information / Invariance / Conservation and Reflection/Refraction Part II

Discontinuity in Space = Time Reversal Break = Conservation Break

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Physically in a two ray problem, with one ray being an incident ray, one has the freedom to choose the incident angle which means that starting at a point x,y the angle of incidence dictates the point at which the ray hits the medium or mirror. Such a two ray approach may apply to reflection from a stationary or moving mirror (constant speed in the negative y direction) or refraction. Fermat's principle, however, requires extremizing total time traveled which means taking a derivative. In general (1) time is written in terms of distance and so the derivative pertains to a "free" spatial variable which is usually the x variable because constraints exist in the y direction. For example a stationary mirror or medium surface exists at a specific y point and this cannot be varied. For a moving mirror the motion in the y direction represents a constraint. Thus it seems that in such problems Fermat's principle relies on a free spatial variable which suggests an invariance in the problem and hence a conservation law in the direction of this free variable as discussed in Part I. This conservation law pertains to a hypothetical velocity which is along the x axis, but represents a hypotenuse, with c/n_1 (n_1 =index of refraction) or relative velocity being a projection of $90-A$ and $90-B$ where A and B are angles of incidence and refraction/reflection. Thus the hypothetical velocity is not the actual physical x velocity motion which is not conserved.

Fermat's principle does not mention momentum, but in this note we ask whether it leads to conservation of momentum in the direction of spatial invariance i.e. the x direction? To make the link we suggest that time reversal symmetry is also required, but that this seems to be linked to spatial invariance in one direction. One may use Fermat's principle to solve reflection from a stationary mirror and find that $A=B$ (angle of incidence=angle of reflection). It is possible to have p_x, p_y and $b p_x, b p_y$ represent the initial and final momenta and still have trigonometric relationships. Time reversal invariance, however, suggests that running a movie forwards and backwards are the same so b must be 1. From this problem one may see that a momentum component may change if there is a discontinuity with the change in the direction normal to this discontinuity. Thus p_y changes to $-p_y$, but p_x remains constant. This is also linked to time reversal symmetry we argue as a discontinuity (step function) may be characterized by one value say n_1 before the discontinuity and n_2 after. Thus running the movie backwards and forwards represents two different problems. In the x direction, however, there may be no discontinuity and so for this component the movie played forwards and backwards is the same. Thus we conclude that momentum conservation exists in the direction of spatial invariance in Fermat's principle. Spatial invariance must exist otherwise one may not take a derivative to time to extremize total time, but this very spatial invariance seems to also suggest time reversal symmetry in the same direction.

In a previous note (2) we argued that given that momentum is of the form $1/\text{wavelength}$ and that wavelength represents resolution, there is a kind of entropy represented by this resolution. Fermat's principle may show that A and B (incident and reflected/refracted angles) differ. This we suggest means that a time reversed picture represents a different physical picture. We have argued above that A and B differing means conservation of momentum in the x direction, but no

conservation of the magnitude of momentum. Thus we argue that a lack of time reversal symmetry with a physical problem suggests different resolutions (i.e. changes in this wavelength based entropy) although the change may be either towards greater or lesser resolution.

Fermat's Principle of Least Time and Spatial Invariance

Fermat's principle of least time for two ray problems already makes use of the idea that light travels in a straight line (which is consistent with the principle).. The idea seems to be to construct an expression for time based on spatial coordinates and then to vary one or more setting the derivative(s) equal to zero to ensure an extremum. Physically one would send in a ray of light with a given incident angle A measured with respect to the normal. In such a case there is nothing to vary in the incident ray. One may only vary the reflected/refracted ray, but both x and y coordinates are indeterminate. As a result this is not this physical scenario which is varied, but rather a somewhat unusual scenario in which one assumes that the x point at which the incident ray hits a surface is unknown.

In a two ray problem such as reflection from a stationary or constantly moving mirror in the negative y direction or refraction with surfaces along the x axis there are y constraints in the problem. Thus one may fix the initial Y value and the final Y (-Y) value of the reflected/refracted ray and only vary x. The form of the extremization is then, using distance = velocity time for refraction with $c/n(i)$ being speed with $n(i)$ being index of refraction:

$$\text{Total time} = \sqrt{YY + xx} n1/ c + \sqrt{YY + (L-x)(L-x)} n2/ c \quad ((2))$$

where L is the length of the interface such that the endpoint of the refracted ray has $y=-Y$.

Then ((2)) may be varied with respect to x and the result set equal to 0. This yield the form:

$$N1 \sin(A) = n2 \sin(B) \quad ((3))$$

This is of the form of a conservation law in the x direction as we have already noted in Part I. Thus Fermat's principle applied to two rays is really an spatial invariance problem which automatically contains a conservation law in the direction of the invariance. Furthermore, this conservation law may be expressed in terms of the conservation of a hypothetical velocity H such that H lies along the x axis, but acts as a hypotenuse with $c/n1$ and $c/n2$ being projections with the angles $90-A$ and $90-B$. This yields ((3)). H is not the physical speed along the x axis. This conservation approach also holds for a mirror moving in the negative y direction with constant speed v. In such a case, n index of refraction is replaced with $1/ v(\text{relative})$ where $v(\text{relative incident}) = c - v \cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative refleted}) = c + v \cos(B)$. ((4))

Reflection From a Stationary Mirror, Fermat's Principle, Time Invariance and Momentum

To try to link Fermat's principle to momentum conservation in the x direction we begin with reflection from a stationary mirror. ((3)) then yields $A=B$ because $n1=n2$. The math is the same whether the final ray moves down (refraction) or up (reflection) because one is minimizing

overall time. Given that $A=B$ from Fermat's least time principle one may ask whether this proves that initial momentum equals reflected momentum. For example, one could have initially p_x, p_y and finally $b p_x, b p_y$ where b is a constant. All trigonometric ratios would remain the same, but incident momentum would not equal final momentum. It seems that one requires an extra invariance beyond x invariance, in particular time reversal invariance. Reflection from a stationary mirror represents the same physical problem whether a movie of the process is run forwards or backwards. Thus given time reversal invariance there is no preferred time so one cannot have p_x in one time range and $b p_x$ in another. One must have $p_x = p_x$ and $p_y = -p_y$. In other words Fermat's least time principle deals with spatial symmetry in one direction, but this should be combined with time reversal symmetry to obtain information about momentum.

The stationary mirror problem also shows that $p_y = -p_y$ i.e. momentum changes because there is a change in the medium or a constraint strictly in the y direction. There is no such constraint or discontinuity in the x direction (i.e. Fermat's invariance d/dx) so $p_x = p_x$. This is why the x direction represents an invariance in Fermat's principle. Thus there seems to be a direct link between spatial invariance and time reversal symmetry in that same direction. Thus the conservation of momentum in that direction seems to follow.

These ideas together with time reversal invariance may be applied to refraction and reflection from a mirror moving in the negative y direction.

The Situation with Momentum

Fermat's principle seems to be one of extremizing time which is based on distance and the relative speed of light. No mention of momentum is made. In fact in (1) it is suggested that conservation of momentum in the x direction yields Snell's law independently of Fermat's principle. We argue that Fermat's principle is directly linked to conservation of momentum in the x direction and also gives a prediction about the magnitude of momentum overall.

Consider the result from Fermat's principle for a two ray problem, namely ((3)). This may be written as:

$$P n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 p \sin(B) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } p \text{ is a constant}$$

If conservation of x momentum holds then:

$$p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B) \quad ((5))$$

where p_1 and p_2 are the magnitudes of the incident and reflected/refracted rays. Comparing ((4)) and ((5)) and noting that p is an arbitrary constant means that:

$$P_1 = n_1 p \text{ and } p_2 = n_2 p \quad ((6))$$

Thus conservation of momentum in the x direction with different A, B values indicates that the magnitudes of the incident and reflected/refracted momenta must be different. Is it possible that ((5)) from Fermat's principle is not equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction?

Consider an incident p_1 making an angle A with the normal. Then:

$p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B)$ where p is an arbitrary constant

((4)) Snell's law shows that the reflected/refracted ray must have an angle of B , but if $p_2 \sin(B)$ is not equal to $n_2 p_1 \sin(A)$ it is not clear what $n_2 p_1 \sin(A)$ represents physically

i.e. a physical quantity would be equal to a mathematical one that has no physical meaning.

In particular, the vectors associated with light are electric and magnetic field which are perpendicular to motion, velocity and momentum. The conserved hypothetical velocity from x invariance in Fermat's principle is not the physical x velocity so it is not the x velocity which is conserved. This leaves only one vector namely momentum and so we suggest that the x component of momentum is conserved. (If this is not the case there would have to be another vector in the problem and it does not seem to exist.)

One may also use the idea of time reversal. A ray moves down towards a mirror that is also moving downward. The time reversed movie shows a ray moving down towards a mirror that is moving up. In the y direction these are physically different scenarios, but not in the x . Thus there is no reason to think that p_x should be different in the x direction. One has to be careful, however, because physical x speed is actually different. For example, for refraction it is $c \sin(A) / n_1$ versus $c \sin(B) / n_2$ and these are not equal. Neither are the relative velocities equal for a moving mirror problem i.e. $\sin(A) v(\text{relative } a)$ and $\sin(B) v(\text{relative } b)$ rather: $\sin(A) / v(\text{relative } a)$ and $\sin(B) / v(\text{relative } b)$ are equal. From the stationary mirror problem it seems that p_x responds to medium changes in the direction normal to the medium. Thus for a refraction surface in the x direction or a mirror with a surface in the x direction moving in the y it seems that momentum in the x direction should not change. There is no medium discontinuity.

This seems like a subtle idea because for refraction p_y encounters a medium discontinuity along y , but p_x does not even though at one time it is moving through medium n_1 and at another through n_2 . Thus it seems that the issue is not moving in different media (for momentum), but encountering a discontinuity. p_x never encounters a discontinuity and so is unchanged. This is directly linked to time reversal symmetry in the x direction. Encountering a discontinuity means defining a time for this encounter. One parameter defines time before the encounter and another after. Thus playing the movie forwards means moving from n_1 to n_2 and backwards moving from n_2 to n_1 . These are the opposite discontinuity changes and so there would be no time reversal symmetry.

Thus we argue that time reversal symmetry together with x invariance from Fermat's principle predicts conservation of momentum in the x direction. In fact we argue that the two are linked. x invariance (Fermat's minimal time principle) suggests that one may shift x . One may make this shift because there is no discontinuity in the x direction along the surface of a medium or mirror. A lack of discontinuity suggests time reversal symmetry in this direction and the two lead to conservation of momentum in the x direction.

Wave Mechanics

One may note from wave mechanics that $E=pc$ for light is equivalent to:

$$A = 0 = -Et + px \quad \text{with } c=x/t \quad ((5))$$

Treating t and x as independent shows that dA/dx partial equals p . Thus there is a link between taking a spatial derivative (as done in Fermat's principle) and the momentum component in that same direction. We note that ((5)) is an extra condition from Fermat's principle, but seems to lend support to the idea of conservation of momentum in the x direction following from the conservation equation obtained using Fermat's principle i.e. $n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ for refraction or $\sin(A) / v(\text{relative } a) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative } b)$ for a moving mirror. This is also linked to taking the derivative of a quantum wavefunction.

Wavelength Entropy

In (2) we suggested that there should exist a wavelength based entropy because wavelength represents resolution. Given that momentum = $\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ a change in momentum suggests a change in wavelength and resolution. In the above discussion we argued that momentum changes when there is a lack of time reversal symmetry in a problem. For refraction and the moving mirror p_x remains constant, but p_y changes so overall p changes due to a lack of time reversal symmetry in the y direction. Thus we argue that a lack of time reversal symmetry leads to changes in a wavelength based entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Fermat's least time principle requires invariance in a spatial dimension because one has to take a derivative of time with respect to a spatial variable. This leads to a conservation equation of hypothetical velocity in the direction of this variable usually x . Hypothetical velocity H is not the actual velocity in the x direction. Rather it is a hypotenuse such that the ray velocity or relative velocity is a projection i.e. $H \sin(A) = c/n_1$ and $H \sin(B) = c/n_2$ for refraction and $H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative } a) = c - v \cos(A)$ and $H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative } b) = c + v \cos(B)$ for a moving mirror problem. Given that there are only two vectors along a light ray namely velocity and momentum p , we argue that the hypothetical velocity conservation law in the x direction should be identical to conservation of momentum in the x direction. To strengthen this idea we argue that one requires both x invariance and time reversal invariance in the x direction to have momentum conservation in this direction. We argue that momentum changes in the direction of a normal to a medium discontinuity. In the x direction there is no medium discontinuity so there should be time reversal invariance in this direction. Otherwise there would be a specific barrier at some x such that times before reaching this barrier would be characterized by one parameter and by another parameter afterwards breaking time reversal symmetry. We argue that a lack of discontinuity in the x direction is the reason that Fermat's principle uses d/dx . Thus x invariance in Fermat's principle suggests time reversal symmetry in this same direction and so suggests conservation of momentum in this direction.

We note that the link between momentum and x is already given in $-Et+px$ which appears in the theory of a photon or follows from $E=pc$ with $c=x/t$. We also note that for a wavelength based entropy, changes in wavelength/resolution are identical to changes in momentum and indicate the breaking of time reversal symmetry in a problem. This break may occur in only one spatial direction e.g. the y direction as in refraction and reflection from a moving mirror.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Two Kinds of Entropy in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2022)